

DEBONDING PREDICTION OF A REINFORCING CFRP PATCH ON CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Concrete substrate structures that are locally connected to or reinforced by a CFRP patch through an adhesive layer are often found in civil engineering. Under given thermomechanical loading, this typically leads to interfacial stresses with stress concentrations at the ends of the patch. In this situation, the onset of debonding cracks can be predicted and assessed by means of the concepts of finite fracture mechanics. In order to make the assessment easy, an approximate closed-form analytical approach is suggested, which is shown to work very efficiently.

KEYWORDS

Patch reinforcement; debonding; finite fracture mechanics.

INTRODUCTION

In civil engineering, there are many potential reasons for using a patch of finite size that is connected to the surface of a concrete element through an adhesive layer. Possible reasons include localized damage, e.g. due to surface cracks, necessary reinforcement or the need to attach a secondary structure, such as a sensor or something similar. Due to their high strength, their corrosion insensitivity and the moderate costs, patches are often made of CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastic). Some overview of the use of CFRP for strengthening and repairing concrete elements is for instance given by a recent review article of Waseem Khairi Mosleh Frhaan et al. (Waseem Khairi Mosleh Frhaan et al., 2021).

The application of CFRP patches is rather simple, but the challenge is to ensure that such patches do not debond under operational and/or environmental thermomechanical loads. Debonding is a typical failure mechanism since the concrete/patch configuration goes along with a significant discontinuity of the geometry and the material properties at the ends of the attached patch. This leads to highly localized stress concentrations of the interfacial stresses in the adhesive layer, but also in the concrete and the patch material. Thus, there is a clear need to know and calculate these stresses and to predict whether the given situation is safe or might lead to debonding failure.

In order to choose an appropriate analysis approach, it makes sense to study the available modelling in the mechanics of adhesive joints, which has a long tradition. A first simple but important theoretical analysis of the stress distribution in single-lap joints was suggested by Volkersen more than 80 years ago (Volkersen, 1938). This approach has been extended and improved in various ways over time, already in 1944 by Goland and Reissner (Goland and Reissner, 1944) and later e.g. by Ojalvo and Eidinoff (Ojalvo and Eidinoff, 1978) and many others. A comprehensive overview of the developed models for adhesive joints has for instance been given by da Silva et al. (da Silva et al., 2009).

The authors of the present paper in particular made good experience with a generalized model of Bigwood and Crocombe (Bigwood and Crocombe, 1989) and extended this in various ways for the case of relatively thick adhesive layers (Methfessel and Becker, 2022). Here, the consideration should focus only on the overlap region, resulting in a local sandwich-like configuration consisting of the two adherends and the adhesive in between. Depending on the given load case, sectional forces or moments or given displacements are applied on the left and right ends of the overlap region. As this kind of model has shown its usefulness in the case of various joint geometries in lightweight construction it will also be chosen as the approach here in the following.

THEORETICAL SETTING AND MODELLING

Sandwich-type model

Let us consider the idealized situation of a concrete base substrate layer of thickness h_2 to which a reinforcing CFRP patch of length l and thickness h_1 is attached by an adhesive layer of thickness t as outlined in Figure 1a. Without loss of generality for the present approach, the CFRP patch is assumed to be a unidirectional fiber reinforced polymer with the fibers aligned in length direction. The concrete layer and the patch may be subjected to external thermomechanical loadings. Following the general sandwich-type approach introduced by Bigwood and Crocombe (Bigwood and Crocombe, 1989) the analysis focuses on the overlap area, as indicated in Figure 1b. The considered standard configuration has the dimensions $l = 100$ mm, $h_1 = 2$ mm and $h_2 = 20$ mm and depth of $d = 100$ mm. The thickness of the adhesive layer is between 0.5 and 2 mm.

Figure 1: Considered sandwich-type model

Within the framework of linear elasticity theory, the concrete substrate layer and the patch layer are idealized by shear deformable plates and introduce a higher-order displacement representation for the adhesive allowing some warping in order to adequately capture the load-transfer behavior. Thus, the horizontal and vertical displacements $u^{(i)}$ and $w^{(i)}$ in the patch layer ($i=1$) and the concrete ($i=2$) are given as

$$u^{(i)}(x,z) = u_0^{(i)}(x) + z_i \psi^{(i)}(x), \quad w^{(i)}(x,z) = w_0^{(i)}(x), \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where $u_0^{(i)}$ and $w_0^{(i)}$ denote the displacements of the layer midplanes and $\psi^{(i)}$ the rotations of their cross sections and z_i are local vertical coordinates starting in the respective midplane. Within the adhesive layer the displacements $u^{(a)}$ and $w^{(a)}$ are modeled by a linear interpolation of the displacements of the concrete substrate and the patch layer at their interfaces to the adhesive, enriched by quadratic and cubic warping deformations $\phi_u(x)$, $\phi_w(x)$ and $\chi_u(x)$, $\chi_w(x)$ in the following manner:

$$u^{(a)}(x,z) = \frac{1}{2}(\hat{u}^{(1)} + \hat{u}^{(2)}) + \frac{z}{t}(\hat{u}^{(2)} - \hat{u}^{(1)}) + \phi_u(x)(1 - \frac{4}{t^2}z^2) + \chi_u(x)(z - \frac{4}{t^2}z^3), \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$w^{(a)}(x,z) = \frac{1}{2}(\hat{w}^{(1)} + \hat{w}^{(2)}) + \frac{z}{t}(\hat{w}^{(2)} - \hat{w}^{(1)}) + \phi_w(x)(1 - \frac{4}{t^2}z^2) + \chi_w(x)(z - \frac{4}{t^2}z^3), \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where

$$\hat{u}^{(1)} = u^{(1)}(z_1 = \frac{h_1}{2}), \quad \hat{u}^{(2)} = u^{(2)}(z_2 = -\frac{h_2}{2}), \quad \hat{w}^{(1)} = w^{(1)}(z_1 = \frac{h_1}{2}), \quad \hat{w}^{(2)} = w^{(2)}(z_2 = -\frac{h_2}{2}). \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Thus, a total of 10 unknown deformation functions $u_0^{(1)}(x)$, $u_0^{(2)}(x)$, ..., $\chi_w(x)$ have been introduced. They must be determined for a respective approximate description of the real deformation of the given structural configuration.

Minimum total potential energy principle

The principle of minimum total potential can be used to determine the unknown deformation functions. The total potential energy Π is composed of an internal and an external part:

$$\Pi = \Pi_{int} + \Pi_{ext}, \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where the internal potential Π_{int} represents the stored strain energy, and the external potential Π_{ext} is related to the acting external forces. For the actual calculation of the strain energy, volume integration must be performed over the strain energy density $\frac{1}{2}\sigma_{ij}\varepsilon_{ij}$, where the strain components ε_{ij} result from standard kinematic relations from the derivatives of the deformations and the stress components σ_{ij} result from the strains through Hooke's law. For the calculation of the external potential, an integration must be performed over the negative product of the applied forces multiplied with the corresponding deformations at the locations of the applied load.

The real deformation of static equilibrium is characterized by minimizing the total potential Π or, equivalently, by a stationary value of the total potential when virtual variations of the deformation field are taken into account:

$$\delta\Pi = 0. \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

For the actual use of Hooke's law in the case of the patch layer ($i=1$) and in the case of the concrete layer ($i=2$), plane stress in z -direction and plane strain in y -direction are assumed. Including thermal strains, Hooke's law for the axial stresses $\sigma_{xx}^{(l)}$ and the shear stresses $\tau_{xz}^{(l)}$ in the case of the patch layer with unidirectionally aligned fibers in the x -direction can be given in the following manner:

$$\sigma_{xx}^{(l)} = Q_{xx}(\varepsilon_{xx}^{(l)} - \alpha_{xx}^{T(l)}\Delta T) - Q_{xy}\alpha_{yy}^{T(l)}\Delta T, \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$\tau_{xz}^{(l)} = \kappa G_{xz}^{(l)}\gamma_{xz}^{(l)}, \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

where

$$Q_{xx} = E_{xx}^{(l)}/(1-\nu_{xy}^{(l)}\nu_{yx}^{(l)}) \text{ and } Q_{xy} = \nu_{xy}^{(l)}E_{yy}^{(l)}/(1-\nu_{xy}^{(l)}\nu_{yx}^{(l)}), \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

In the case of the isotropic concrete layer Hooke's law can be given as:

$$\sigma_{xx}^{(2)} = E^{(2)}(\varepsilon_{xx}^{(2)} - (1 + \nu^{(2)})\alpha_T^{(2)}\Delta T)/(1 - \nu^{(2)^2}), \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$\tau_{xz}^{(2)} = \kappa G^{(2)}\gamma_{xz}^{(2)}, \quad \text{with } \kappa = 5/6. \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

Within the adhesive layer, the current model also includes strains ε_{zz} and stresses σ_{zz} in thickness direction. Again, assuming a plane strain state in the y -direction, isotropic Hooke's law can be expressed as follows:

$$\sigma_{xx}^{(a)} = E^* ((1 - \nu^{(a)})\varepsilon_{xx} + \nu^{(a)}\varepsilon_{zz} - (1 + \nu^{(a)})\alpha_T\Delta T), \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

$$\sigma_{zz}^{(a)} = E^* (\nu^{(a)}\varepsilon_{xx} + (1 - \nu^{(a)})\varepsilon_{zz} - (1 + \nu^{(a)})\alpha_T\Delta T), \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

$$\tau_{xz}^{(a)} = G^{(a)}\gamma_{xz}, \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

where

$$E^* = E^{(a)}/((1 + \nu^{(a)})(1 - 2\nu^{(a)})) \text{ and } G^{(a)} = E^{(a)}/(2(1 + \nu^{(a)})). \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

System of differential equations and its solution

When the variation of the total potential energy is actually performed, taking into account variations of all ten deformation functions and summing up the integrals over the concrete, the patch and the adhesive region, this eventually leads to a set of ten coupled linear differential equations with constant

coefficients and corresponding boundary conditions. The differential equations are of second order for the unknown deformation functions and can be solved by standard methods. For formal simplicity, the ten equations of second order can be transformed into a first-order system of twenty differential equations for the ten unknown deformation functions and their ten first derivatives, which can be formally combined to a vector $\mathbf{z}(x)$ of twenty unknown functions:

$$\mathbf{Az}' + \mathbf{Bz} = \mathbf{d} , \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

where the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} and the right-hand side vector \mathbf{d} are not given here in detail but can be found in the paper of Methfessel and Becker from 2022 for the case of isotropic layers (Methfessel and Becker, 2022).

The solution of this non-homogeneous system of differential equations consists of the sum of a particular solution and the general homogeneous solution:

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{z}_p + \mathbf{z}_h . \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

A particular solution can be obtained by a general constant approach with a vector of unknown constant entries. Inserting this into the system of differential equations yields the unknown constants and thus the particular solution \mathbf{z}_p .

For the general homogeneous solution, the exponential solution approach of the form $\mathbf{z}_h = \mathbf{v}e^{\lambda x}$ is inserted into the system of differential equations, which leads to an eigenvalue system. The eigenvalues λ can then be calculated from the condition

$$\det(\mathbf{A}\lambda + \mathbf{B}) = 0 . \quad \text{Eq. 18}$$

For the structural configurations studied here, this results in six real non-zero eigenvalues, four pairs of complex conjugated eigenvalues and six zero eigenvalues (in total twenty). The corresponding eigenvectors \mathbf{v} are determined by solving

$$(\mathbf{A}\lambda + \mathbf{B})\mathbf{v} = 0 . \quad \text{Eq. 19}$$

In the case of the zero eigenvalues, some so-called higher-order eigenvectors might be required (Methfessel and Becker, 2022). The general homogeneous solution of the system of differential equations then results from a linear combination of the twenty obtained exponential solutions with twenty free constants. These free constants have to be identified in a final step from the given boundary conditions. The given load is introduced into the structure via corresponding cross-sectional forces, which are applied as dynamic boundary conditions. However, in order to avoid pure rigid body motions and to ensure a statically determined system, there should also be corresponding geometric boundary conditions. Once the constants have been identified the resultant displacements and, with them and their derivatives, also the resulting strains and stresses can be evaluated.

STRESS ANALYSIS

The presented approach is based on displacements. This ensures continuity of all displacements across the concrete-adhesive and patch-adhesive interfaces. It enables an easy fulfilment of given geometric boundary conditions and it allows a simple comparison with deformation results obtained numerically by confirmatory finite element analyses. The accompanying stresses can be obtained in a straightforward manner by Hooke's law. Compared to the still widely used models of Volkersen (Volkersen, 1938), Goland and Reissner (Goland and Reissner, 1944), and Ojalvo and Eidinoff (Ojalvo and Eidinoff, 1978) the included warping deformation modes of the adhesive layer in the current approach can be expected to lead to more realistic interface stresses. This is advantageous in regard of a more realistic prediction of debonding failure. With regard to the resultant interface stresses, a generic example under a mechanical and a thermal load is considered. The example consists of a base concrete substrate layer of 100 mm length and 20 mm thickness that can be considered as a local

section of a larger concrete structure (where it does not matter whether it is steel-reinforced or not). A unidirectional CFRP patch of 2 mm thickness is attached to the concrete by an adhesive layer of epoxy polymer of thickness t . For the concrete, a Young's modulus of $E^{(2)}=30$ GPa, a Poisson's ratio of $\nu^{(2)}=0.2$ and a coefficient of thermal expansion of $\alpha_T^{(2)}=10\cdot 10^{-6}$ 1/K are assumed. For the adhesive, an epoxy is chosen with the properties $E^{(a)}=2,7$ GPa, $\nu^{(a)}=0.36$ and $\alpha_T^{(a)}=65\cdot 10^{-6}$ 1/K. The characteristics for the patch are taken from T300, a transversely anisotropic elastic CFRP with $E_{11}^{(1)}=135$ GPa, $E_{22}^{(1)}=E_{33}^{(1)}=10$ GPa, $\nu_{12}^{(1)}=\nu_{13}^{(1)}=0,27$, $\nu_{23}^{(1)}=0,3$, $G_{12}^{(1)}=G_{13}^{(1)}=5$ GPa und $G_{23}^{(1)}=3,85$ GPa. The coefficients of thermal expansion are $\alpha_{11}^{(1)}=-0,6\cdot 10^{-6}$ 1/K und $\alpha_{22}^{(1)}= \alpha_{33}^{(1)}=10\cdot 10^{-6}$ 1/K.

Patch under mechanical load

For a first basic understanding of the interaction of the CFRP patch with the concrete substrate, a homogeneous tensile loading of the concrete by $\sigma_{xx}^{(2)}=1$ MPa is considered. This is below the assumed tensile strength of 2.2 MPa and may locally result from the overall bending of a large reinforced concrete beam or a similar loading. Of course, local tensile stresses are not really what concrete elements are designed for, but it is still very essential to assess their possibly critical effects. The potentially critical issue is that there is a load transfer through the adhesive layer to the very stiff and strong CFRP patch, with some stress concentration at the ends of the patch and with local transversal stresses σ_{zz} (so-called peeling stresses) and τ_{xz} (transversal shear stresses). These stresses must be continuous across the layer interfaces and are most critical in terms of the strength in the concrete substrate (at the interface to the adhesive layer), since the concrete material has the lowest respective strength properties. As a consequence, the stresses $\sigma_{zz}^{(2)}$ and $\tau_{xz}^{(2)}$ at $z_2=-h_2/2$ within the concrete layer are of paramount interest.

The stress distribution along the x -axis resulting from the implemented closed-form analytical approach described above is shown in Figure 2 for a structure with an adhesive thickness $t=1$ mm. It can be clearly seen that there is a considerable stress concentration at $x=-l/2$. This indicates that the CFRP patch tends to delaminate at its ends, which is of course an undesirable failure mechanism.

Figure 2: Resultant stress distribution along x -axis for the mechanical load case

For comparison and as a validation Figure 2 also includes the corresponding stress results of an accompanying detailed finite element analysis performed with the commercial finite element software ABAQUS, employing a very fine mesh of continuum elements within each layer, with a total size of about 75 000 degrees of freedom. The finite element results reveal that the peeling stress σ_{zz} at the ends of the patch is even higher than that of our current analysis. This is because, strictly speaking, according to the theory of elasticity, there is even a stress singularity at the ends of the patch. However, this is not helpful for design purposes, as it could lead to the unrealistic conclusion that

material failure will always occur. However, in the overall character of the stress distributions, the finite element result shows that the presented analytical approach goes in the right direction. It is also a characteristic of the generally applied bonding analyses of Goland and Reissner (Goland and Reissner, 1944) and Ojalvo and Eidinoff (Ojalvo and Eidinoff, 1978) that they yield only finite stresses, but not singular stresses.

Patch under thermal load

In addition to the pure mechanical load case, the model is also applied to a thermal load case. Therefore, a temperature field with a temperature increase of $\Delta T = 10$ K is uniformly applied on the three-layer structure. Due to the different thermal behavior of the layers, recognizable by their different coefficients of thermal expansion, a complex stress distribution is produced, as seen in Figure 3. While concrete and epoxy are isotropic, the CFRP has different coefficients of thermal expansion in different directions, depending on the fiber orientation. The thickness of the adhesive layer here is $t = 0.5$ mm. As illustrated in Figure 3 the stress distributions for the peeling stress σ_{zz} along the interface between epoxy and concrete have a high peak at the edge of the structure. Just as in the mechanical load case, delamination is therefore conceivable and must be prevented. Especially the high peeling stresses can potentially exceed the tensile strength of the concrete. Figure 3 also shows that the stress results of the analytical model are in satisfying agreement with those of the finite element analysis.

Figure 3: Resultant stress distribution along x -axis for the thermal load case

DEBONDING PREDICTION

In order to ensure the function of the CFRP patch, debonding failure must not occur. On the other hand, the patch is prone to debonding at its ends because of stress concentrations in the interfacial stress distributions of τ_{xz} and σ_{zz} . In the present study the concrete material directly at the concrete/adhesive interface is considered as the weakest part, since concrete has a very low tensile and shear strength and also a very low fracture toughness. As the stresses τ_{xz} and σ_{zz} are continuous across the interface, they can be calculated within the adhesive layer directly at the interface, where the local z -coordinate is equal to $t/2$.

The simplest way to assess debonding would be to compare the local interfacial stresses with the respective strength values. However, this does not lead to realistic predictions, since structures can generally withstand local stresses exceeding the strength values as long as they are sufficiently

localized. For instance, it is well known that the stresses at the tips of a crack in a plate become infinite, but for sufficiently short cracks this can be sustained. Incidentally, a sufficiently refined analysis of the patch/concrete configuration in the context of elasticity theory would also reveal some stress singularities at the ends of the concrete/patch interface, but these do not necessarily always lead to debonding. Thus, a local, purely stress-based assessment is not the right way to go.

An alternative could be the consideration of the (differential) energy release rate associated with the growth of a potential debonding crack, as it is a well-established concept in fracture mechanics. However, in the case of the concrete/patch configuration without pre-crack, this would lead to an energy release rate that starts at zero and therefore is not potentially damaging. Thus, it is also not a way to predict debonding.

The concept of finite fracture mechanics

A way out of this challenging situation is the concept of a coupled criterion within the framework of finite fracture mechanics, as it has been suggested by Leguillon (Leguillon, 2002). This means that the instantaneous initiation of a crack of finite length is postulated only if a stress-based strength criterion is satisfied and if, at the same time, the energy released in this transition is large enough to overcome the underlying fracture toughness. The strength-of-materials subcriterion requires that an equivalent stress $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma})$ must exceed the material strength σ_c for the set of Γ_c of all points of the potential crack:

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}(x)) \geq \sigma_c \text{ for all } x \in \Gamma_c. \quad \text{Eq. 20}$$

The energy-based fracture mechanics subcriterion with an appropriately chosen function g can be formulated as

$$g(\bar{G}_I(\Delta A), \bar{G}_{II}(\Delta A)) \geq G_c. \quad \text{Eq. 21}$$

Herein, ΔA denotes the surface area of the generated crack Γ_c , G_c is the fracture toughness, and the quantities \bar{G}_i denote the so-called incremental energy release rates of the crack-opening modes I and II , defined as the released energy $-\Delta \Pi$ during the initiation of a crack related to the respective crack size ΔA :

$$\bar{G}_i = -\Delta \Pi_i / \Delta A, \quad i \in \{I, II\} \quad \text{Eq. 22}$$

According to the coupled criterion, a crack of length Δa and area ΔA is initiated instantaneously if both subcriteria are fulfilled simultaneously:

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}(x)) \geq \sigma_c \text{ for all } x \in \Gamma_c \quad \wedge \quad g(\bar{G}_I(\Delta A), \bar{G}_{II}(\Delta A)) \geq G_c \quad \text{Eq. 23}$$

For a given load this coupled criterion can be used to predict failure if it is fulfilled, or to ensure structural integrity if the coupled criterion is not fulfilled. Moreover, the coupled criterion can also be used to predict the effective strength of a given structural situation: Then, the minimal load satisfying the coupled criterion must be found. This corresponds to the solution of a respective optimization problem, which generally has to be solved iteratively.

To account for the effect of initiated delamination cracks along the concrete/adhesive interface or equivalent failure along the concrete top position at $z_2 = -h_2/2$ in the closed-form analytical model described above, the displacement representation according to Equations 2 and 3 is modified to allow separation of the adhesive from the concrete within the range of the considered crack length Δa . The incremental energy release rates can then be calculated using Irwin's crack closure integral in the following manner:

$$\bar{G}_I = \frac{1}{2} \int \sigma_{zz}(w^{(2)} - w^{(a)}) dx, \quad \bar{G}_{II} = \frac{1}{2} \int \tau_{xz}(u^{(2)} - u^{(a)}) dx, \quad \text{Eq. 24}$$

where the integration is performed from $x = -l/2$ to $x = -l/2 + \Delta a$.

For the currently studied concrete/patch configuration, the stress criterion according to Equation 20 is specifically chosen as a quadratic superposition of the interface normal and shear stresses:

$$\sigma_{zz}^2 + \tau_{xz}^2 \geq \sigma_c^2. \quad \text{Eq. 25}$$

For the energy subcriterion, simply the total incremental energy release rate is taken:

$$\bar{G}_{tot} = \bar{G}_I + \bar{G}_{II} \geq G_c. \quad \text{Eq. 26}$$

For the current calculations, the tensile strength σ_c is assumed to be 2.2 MPa and the fracture toughness G_c is assumed to be 0.0032 N/mm.

Patch under mechanical load

In order to determine the mechanical load under which the patch is expected to debond, the mechanical load was iterated and the corresponding optimization problem was solved. This leads to the behavior of the incremental energy release rate as a function of the delamination crack length Δa , as shown in Figure 4. As can be seen, the mode I energy release rate \bar{G}_I and as a consequence also the total incremental energy release rate \bar{G}_{tot} have a local maximum for a rather short crack length of about 0.3 mm and this maximum just touches the level of the fracture toughness G_c . This situation is given for a total applied load of 19.1 kN for a concrete layer with a width of 100 mm.

Figure 4: Incremental energy release rate as a function of the debonding crack length for the mechanical load case

Figure 5 shows the effects of varying adhesive layer thicknesses on the critical failure load. It can be seen that an increase in the thickness of the adhesive layer is accompanied by some increase in the critical failure load, although this effect is not very strong. For comparison and validation purposes, Figure 5 also includes the corresponding results based on accompanying finite element calculations where the same type of hybrid failure criterion was applied to determine the mechanical strength. Obviously, the agreement with the predictions of the closed-form modelling approach is rather good, with a deviation of roughly 10 percent. This is remarkable in the sense that the newly presented model is quite simple and highly efficient. It can also be observed that the respective predictions are conservative, which is important for the practical application.

Figure 5: Effect of the thickness of the adhesive layer on the failure load for the mechanical load case

Figure 5 also shows the identified debonding crack length Δa_c for the critical situation. For a thickness of the adhesive layer of 1mm or more, the situation of the incremental energy release rate corresponds to that shown in Figure 4, where the peak value touches the fracture toughness level. However, for a thinner adhesive layer of 0.5 mm, the situation is different: Here, the incremental energy release rate reaches the critical value only for significantly longer cracks.

In this studied example, the calculated failure load of 19.1 kN corresponds to an averaged stress of 9,55 MPa acting on the concrete layer. Obviously, this is far beyond the concrete strength and will never be reached. Thus, the studied debonding failure mode will actually not happen in the assumed geometry, and in this regard the CFRP patch is „safely bonded“. The performed strength assessment should be understood as focusing on one particular failure mode, the debonding of the applied patch. Of course, the considered structural configuration should also be checked for competing failure modes, such as the individual inplane failure of the layers involved.

Patch under thermal load

For the consideration of the thermal load case, the optimization is modified. Instead of iterating a mechanical force F , a temperature change ΔT is now iterated against a stress-free manufacturing condition until a critical temperature change has been determined. As an example, Figure 6 shows the energy release rate curves for a temperature change of 23.7 K applied to a structure with an adhesive layer thickness of 0.5 mm. As can be seen in the figure, the contribution from the mode I energy release rate \bar{G}_I contributes significantly to the total energy release rate. The mode II energy release rate \bar{G}_{II} is significantly lower and increases only very slowly with the crack length. In this load case, again the front peak of the total energy release rate enables the fulfillment of the energy criterion.

Figure 6: Incremental energy release rate as a function of the debonding crack length for the thermal load case

After optimization, the critical temperature changes and the corresponding crack lengths shown in Figure 7 are obtained. The adhesive layer thickness is changed step by step and its effect on the critical temperature changes is illustrated. As can be seen, the analytical results and the results from finite element analyses only show small differences, where the analytical results are always more conservative. Looking at the critical temperature changes, failure is more likely to occur with increasing adhesive layer thickness. At the same time, the crack lengths also become longer. Therefore, from a design point of view, a thin adhesive layer is more advisable, which deforms less with temperature changes.

Figure 7: Effect of the thickness of the adhesive layer on the failure load for the thermal load case

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, failure estimation of CFRP reinforced concrete elements is performed using finite fracture mechanics. For this purpose, a stress and an energy criterion need to be evaluated that predict failure of the structure if both are satisfied simultaneously. Failure in this case primarily means the formation of cracks, which in a three-layer composite typically occur at the layer interface in the

horizontal direction, thus in this case between the concrete and the adhesive layer or as pure concrete cracks close to the layer interface. Apart from this, other pure concrete cracks are of course also possible, which are not necessarily in the vicinity of the patch. These could be studied as another potential failure mechanism also by means of finite fracture mechanics.

The present structure is analyzed for both mechanical and thermal failure. By means of an adapted calculation method in each case, it is thus possible to determine the critical tensile force in the concrete, or the critical temperature change, at which instantaneous formation of a finite-length crack occurs. The model can be applied to different geometries and load cases and covers isotropic and orthotropic material behavior of the adherends.

Compared with finite element analyses, both critical loads and fracture lengths agree well. The critical loads are always estimated a bit more conservatively. However, the evaluation with the analytical model is much faster and more efficient than that with the finite element model. Especially, the iterative determination of the critical load and the calculation of many cracked configurations takes a long time in a finite element analysis with a sufficiently fine mesh. In contrast, the analytical model based on simple fundamental equations provides a highly efficient solution.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.